

CMIP Panel Terms of Reference

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This document complies with the [WCRP Guidelines on Membership and Responsibilities](#) and ensures that the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) Panel of the Working Group on Coupled Modelling (WGCM) has in place transparent, accountable, and effective procedures which honour the commitment and contribution of volunteering individuals, and ensure fairness, inclusion, and equity. Should the WCRP and/or Earth System Modelling and Observations (ESMO) Core Project guidelines change, this document will be updated.

Definitions

- **Body** - Body to whom the ToRs apply, the CMIP Panel.
- **Parent Body (PB)** - the WGCM is the Parent Body of the CMIP Panel to whom the Body immediately reports to.
- **Parent Body Liaison Member (PBLM)** - member of the WGCM appointed as key liaison point to perform specified duties set out in the ToR. If that member is unable to carry out duties, the WGCM can appoint a temporary replacement or replace the member holding this position.
- **Task Team (TT)** - a group of people temporarily working together to accomplish a specific task/set of tasks within the planned programme of work of a Body. Once that work is completed, the TT is closed.
- **Ex-officio member** - member of the Body by virtue of occupying an existing position within another organisation/body of importance or relevance to the Body. An ex-officio member is someone who holds a relevant position within a relevant committee/body/organisation. The membership position is assigned to the individual holding the office. Their membership ceases when they cease to hold that office. Their successor becomes the replacement ex-officio member.
- **Emeritus member** - a member who has reached their term limit/is no longer in employment but is invited to stay on the Body in an advisory capacity.
- **Conflict of interest:** A “conflict of interest” refers to any current professional, financial or other interest which could: i) significantly impair the individual’s objectivity in carrying out duties and responsibilities for the [Body], or ii) create an unfair advantage for any person or organisation. For the purposes of this policy, circumstances that could lead a reasonable person to question an individual’s objectivity, or whether an unfair advantage has been created, constitute a potential conflict of interest. These potential conflicts are subject to disclosure. [as defined by the IPCC in their [Conflict of Interest Policy](#)]

Purpose

1. The CMIP Panel is a panel of the WGCM, which is a Working Group of the ESMO Core Project of WCRP. The CMIP Panel is supported by the CMIP International Project Office.
2. The CMIP Panel was initiated in 1995.

3. Goal of the CMIP Panel: The CMIP Panel is a WCRP WGCM panel charged with focus on overseeing the evolving design of Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) and with coordinating the various activities contributing to the science and impact of CMIP.
4. Objectives of the Body:
 - 4.1. The Panel provides recommendations, proposals, and insight to the WGCM, which is the decision-making body and will report to the WGCM, and ESMO SSG as directed, and brief other relevant WCRP committees and panels on progress, status, and plans for activities overseen by the CMIP Panel.
 - 4.2. The Panel works to empower modelling centres to deliver globally coordinated multi-model ensembles to further understanding of the climate system and provide foundations for climate mitigation and adaptation policy.
 - 4.3. The Panel promotes a transparent and open process to ensure equality of access to the process and of input to requirements and design choices.
 - 4.4. The Panel ensures transparency in experimental design and provenance of resulting data.
 - 4.5. The Panel assists the climate modelling community in responding constructively to policy needs (e.g., IPCC, Global Stocktake, national assessments) while minimising disruption to research programmes.
 - 4.6. The Panel provides support and coordination to community initiatives which exploit global Earth System Models and their data in terms of adhering to CMIP protocols and data standardisation requirements.
 - 4.7. The Panel may establish task teams on an ad-hoc basis to fulfil its goals, and along with the WGCM Infrastructure Panel (WIP), coordinates the work of any CMIP task teams to facilitate development of protocols. Protocols covers coordinated experiment design, any necessary auxiliary datasets e.g. for forcing, data protocols, and data publication to optimise the impact of resource investment in ground-breaking climate computations by maximising data use and re-use.
 - 4.8. The CMIP Panel works closely with the WGCM Infrastructure Panel (WIP), which coordinates infrastructure support for CMIP and is responsible for many of the technical specifications for model output.

Below this point, except for (26), no need to change anything unless the Body has a specific cause to change them. Bodies are, of course, empowered to change these rules by a vote plus ESMO approval.

Term

5. The CMIP Panel as a panel of WGCM, remains active until a decision is made to close it by the WGCM and ESMO SSG.

Membership

TYPES & DECISION MAKING

6. There are three types of members: Voting members, Ex-officio members and Emeritus members. All members with voting rights must be employed by an organisation/institution.
 - 6.1. A voting member of an ESMO body (Task Teams and ex-officio positions excluded) cannot hold more than one membership within ESMO.
 - 6.2. Voting members have voting rights in all matters.
 - 6.3. Ex-officio members have no voting rights but if the decision is relevant to them, they can be invited to speak, at co-chairs' discretion, before the vote is made.
 - 6.4. Emeritus members have no voting rights.
 - 6.5. Members of CMIP Panel will:
 - a. have regard to the CMIP IPO [Best Practice Note on Conflicts of Interest](#)
 - b. review before each meeting, where decisions and/or recommendations are being made, whether there are any interests which may conflict with their duties as members of the CMIP Panel and, if so, disclose them to the co-chairs and supporting CMIP IPO staff
 - c. be asked by the Co-chairs of CMIP Panel at each meeting to confirm they have carried out such a review and made such disclosure
 - d. not participate in any activity of CMIP Panel in relation to which they believe they have a conflict or possible conflict of interest without the consent of the CMIP Panel Co-chairs, who will manage the conflict in accordance with the Best Practice Note.
7. Decision making is by consensus. However, if this is not possible, a vote should be taken. For a decision to be approved, there must be a 2/3 majority vote with 75% quorum of Voting Members.
 - 7.1. The Parent Body (WGCM) should be notified of any significant decisions within the annual report (see 34). In some circumstances, particularly where there are significant community coordination/resources implications, the CMIP Panel may wish to seek endorsement from the WGCM for a decision.
 - 7.2. If a decision from the CMIP Panel is pending on WGCM approval, and the WGCM liaison member does not answer within one month and after two reminders, the decision can be considered as approved. The last reminder must state that "*the decision will be considered as approved in absence of answer by [a given date], as per the Terms of Reference*".

SIZE

8. In accordance with the ESMO ToRs, membership consists of two co-chairs, a minimum of 5 and a maximum of 15 members, including the Voting members and co-chairs. Emeritus members and ex-officio members can be appointed if needed. Emeritus and ex-officio members do not count within the maximum member number.

TERM, TERMINATION & EXTENSION

9. In alignment with the [WCRP Guidelines on Membership and Responsibilities](#) (WCRP guidelines) all appointments are initially for a maximum of 4 years, with up to two 2-year extensions possible.
10. The four-year terms of the two co-chairs shall be staggered by at least one calendar year as far as possible to prevent gaps in leadership and enhance resilience.

- 10.1. When an existing member moves up to one of the two co-chair positions, the appointment length “clock” is reset, with the condition that the member can serve on the committee up to a maximum of 10 years altogether. Only in rare circumstances (which would require ESMO SSG approval) would any individual serve on the same committee for longer than 10 years. Permission to do so must be sought from the WGCM and ESMO using the form in Annex B.
- 10.2. For an outgoing chair or co-chair, an extension of up to 1 year as a voting member is possible, where a handover period is deemed necessary concurrently with the first year of a successor co-chair.
- 10.3. Outgoing chairs/co-chairs, along with any other members who have exceeded their term, can be made *Emeritus members* at the discretion of the current co-chairs and WGCM.
11. Emeritus members have their membership reviewed annually, there is no limit on this term.
12. The relevance of Ex-Officio membership is reviewed every 4 years.
13. All members can resign from their position at any point and are encouraged to give three months’ notice. Resigning members are encouraged to first discuss their circumstances with a chair/co-chairs. It might be more suitable to pause the membership in circumstances where ability to participate is restricted for a specific period (e.g., parental leave), or change the membership type. A membership pause is excluded from the service calculation in 10.1.

MEMBER APPOINTMENT

14. Co-chairs, Voting and Emeritus members are appointed based on their personal experience and expertise and should be willing to represent relevant geographical or specialist science/technical areas, beyond their existing affiliations, as set out in the membership call text and table of Body members (25).
15. All new appointments should be made with consideration of compliance with the [WCRP Guidelines on Membership and Responsibilities](#) on diversity. Restrictions may be included to address under-representation within the Body. An open call should be issued by the CMIP IPO with a specification of requirements in line with membership responsibilities set by the co-chairs. The open call should run for at least a month. A deadline will be set for applications, which will be collected by the CMIP IPO. The CMIP IPO will coordinate all open calls for all CMIP bodies, which can be requested through standard reporting mechanisms or by special need.
16. All applications should contain as a minimum:
 - a. A statement (up to 500 words) demonstrating why they are a good candidate for that position
 - b. A 1 page Curriculum Vitae (CV)
17. For Voting member positions, the applications will be collected by the CMIP IPO and issued to the selection committee to make a decision. Decision options are Appoint, Waitlist and Reject. Applicants should be excluded from any selection committees/votes relating to this process.
 - 17.1. For regular members positions, the co-chairs are responsible for the selection. A shortlist of minimum two candidates and maximum three candidates should be provided in priority order from 1 (with 1 being the first choice). The length of the shortlist can be extended if several positions are available. The WGCM liaison member either approves or proposes a new ranking until agreement with the CMIP Panel co-chairs is reached.

17.2. For Chair/Co-chair positions, the CMIP Panel (voting members only) is responsible for the selection. A shortlist of maximum three candidates should be provided in priority order from 1 (with 1 being the first choice). The WGCM co-chairs either approve or propose a new ranking until agreement with the CMIP Panel is reached.

18. Members involved in shortlisting can refer to the WGCM, and ESMO SSG, for arbitration.

19. No communication to candidates can take place until WGCM liaison member approval has been obtained.

REVOKING MEMBERSHIP

20. Unproductive members may be removed by the CMIP Panel co-chairs if any of the following criteria are met:

20.1. Two unexcused meetings in a row.

20.2. Violation of the [WCRP code of conduct](#).

20.3. Undeclared conflict of interest.

21. All member removals, including the reasoning for the removal and a copy of the removal communication, must be shared with the WGCM and ESMO IPO.

Roles and Responsibilities

22. It is the responsibility of all members to ensure the activities of the CMIP Panel are in accordance with the Goal and objectives set out in (3) and (4).

23. It is the responsibility of all members to ensure the CMIP IPO supporting their activity has up to date contact details for them and is notified of any changes to role and employing institution.

24. Co-chairs are responsible for reviewing the table of member types every two years. Any amendments to the table should be issued as a new version of this ToR (51).

25a. TABLE: MEMBER TYPES OF CMIP (CORE) PANEL, limited to 5-15 Members by (8)

Member type	Appointment process	Term	Responsibilities /Justification
Co-chairs (2)	Open Call	4+2+2 years	<p>The co-chairs' roles are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. To provide leadership of the Panel and vision and drive to achieve the Panel's aims and objectives. b. To chair meetings of the Panel. c. To ensure development and delivery of the relevant phase of CMIP. d. To ensure coordination of and liaison between its task teams, with the support of the IPO. e. To make operational decisions about the work of the Panel between meetings. f. To liaise with the WGCM co-chairs and the WIP co-chairs and provide guidance to the CMIP IPO regarding project priorities. g. To actively promote the work of the Panel. h. To report, as relevant, to WGCM, ESMO and WCRP Joint Scientific Committee (JSC).
Voting members – Core Panel (up to 6 plus co-chairs)	Open Call	4+2+2 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Attend and contribute to meetings, typically convened monthly, to drive progress and review issues and risks arising in the delivery of CMIP. b. Work with other Panel members to develop white papers and other publications as relevant and to support CMIP development and impact. c. Ensure adequate availability to be able to respond to requests for support from Panel co-chairs and the IPO. d. Promote the work of the Panel and CMIP within their own networks and wider community. e. Commit to promoting diversity, equality, inclusivity, and environmental sustainability within the CMIP project. f. Core Panel members will assist the co-chairs with the core delivery of CMIP and liaison with the task teams.

Ex-officio (2)	WIP Co-Chairs	Reviewed every 4 years	Provide linkage to WGCM Infrastructure Panel
Ex-officio (1)	WGCM Liaison Member	Reviewed every 4 years	Provide linkage to WGCM (Parent Body)
Emeritus (1)	Body & PBLM (annual review)	1 year annually renewed	Provide historical knowledge and experienced insight

To note, a CMIP Panel member is assigned to each task team the CMIP Panel creates. To avoid conflicts of interest, where possible task team co-leads will not be CMIP Panel members. The CMIP Panel welcomes attendance of its task team co-leads at, what it terms, “Full Panel” meetings. For the avoidance of doubt, “Extended Panel” is considered a subsidiary body of the CMIP Core Panel

25b. TABLE: MEMBER TYPES OF CMIP PANEL (EXTENDED PANEL), a subsidiary of the CMIP PANEL (CORE)

CMIP task team (TT) co-leads (<i>including Fresh Eyes on CMIP steering group science co-leads</i>)	Open Call	4+2+2 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Report on areas of responsibility (TT), provide relevant material to support Panel decision making, and adopt actions as needed. b. Develop and deliver white papers and other publications as relevant to the goals and activities of the TT. c. Manage risks relevant to specific tasks of the TT in close coordination with the Core Panel and IPO. d. TT Co-leads attendance at Full Panel meetings is welcomed but remains optional and should be driven by relevance of the agenda to their TT or area of expertise.
Ex-officio (1)	CORDEX SAT Co-Chair	Reviewed every 4 years	Provide linkage to Coordinated Regional Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX)
Ex-officio (1)	VIACS Advisory Board	Reviewed every 4 years	Provide linkage to Vulnerability, Impacts, Adaptation and Climate Services (VIACS) Advisory Board
Ex-officio (1)	ScenarioMIP	Reviewed every 4 years	Provide linkage to ScenarioMIP and Integrated Assessment Modelling (IAM) Community

Meetings and deliverables

26. The full and Core Panels shall meet virtually or in person on at least a quarterly basis with additional meetings as required e.g., during periods of high activity.
27. Meetings will be organised by the CMIP IPO and chaired by one of the co-chairs. The CMIP IPO will provide the secretariat function for any Panel meetings in accordance with (35).
28. CMIP meetings and events shall be professional, respectful, and harassment-free environments for all participants in line with the [WCRP code of conduct](#).
29. The majority of Panel meetings will be held virtually with in-person meetings arranged as required and with due consideration of carbon impact. Meeting timings will be rotated as far as possible to ensure members in certain time zones are not disadvantaged.
30. The agenda will be developed by the IPO and co-chairs and circulated to Panel members in advance of any meeting. Meeting papers should be circulated at least three working days in advance.
31. Meeting formats will reflect the nature of, and topics for, discussion and may include small group breakout sessions.
32. Non-members may be invited to present or contribute to Panel meetings.
33. An annual meeting with WGCM will be held with the CMIP Panel Co-chairs.
34. An annual report will be supplied to the WGCM in the format and timeframe requested by them, in line with JSC reporting requirements. This will set out the achievements, significant decisions and recommendations, issues, plans, membership, and financial requests for the next 2 years and updates on Subsidiary Bodies.

Publications

35. All official publications of any activity within CMIP, except for those controlled by the ESMO IPO, or academic or professional publishers, must be published by the CMIP IPO. Where the CMIP IPO has delegated the publication to another IPO, the CMIP IPO must have sight of the final version prior to publication. Publications co-authored by members as part of the CMIP Panel goals and objectives published by an ordinary peer-reviewing publisher should be provided to the CMIP IPO and included in the annual report.

Code of conduct

36. All activities of the CMIP Panel (Core Panel and Full Panel), and its representations on behalf of it by its members and members of its subsidiary bodies, must be made in compliance with the [WCRP Code of Conduct](#).

Subsidiary Bodies

A list of all subsidiary bodies of the CMIP Panel can be found at: <https://bit.ly/CMIP-subsubsidiarybodies>

TASK TEAMS

37. The CMIP Panel may set up a Task Team. Notification of a Task Team creation should be submitted by the co-chairs to ESMO SSG following a specific template (see Annex A).
38. Recommendations for stand-alone CMIP Panel Task Teams should be submitted to the ESMO for approval prior to initiation. It is anticipated that approval will be granted within 30 working days of receipt of Notification.
39. Each Task Team should have at least one Voting Member of CMIP Panel as a Task Team member. Non-members, deemed associates, can be added. A list of members should be held by the co-chairs and the supporting project office.
40. Task Team activities must comply with the CMIP Panel's Terms of Reference. The Voting Member(s) on the Task Team are responsible for this compliance.
41. It is recommended that each Task Team has two co-leads appointed for resilience. These can be self-appointed or appointed through an open call, as deemed appropriate by the CMIP Panel.
42. If a Task Team has delivered on the task(s) assigned by the CMIP Panel, the team will be closed, and letters of thanks issued from the CMIP Panel co-chairs to the Task Team members in recognition of their contribution.
43. Should a Task Team be unable to progress delivery of the assigned task(s) or adjudication be required, the lead must report this to the CMIP Panel co-chairs.

STAKEHOLDER PANEL(S)

44. The CMIP Panel can set up and close stakeholder panels in accordance with the delivery of its goal and objectives (3) (4).
45. A stakeholder panel should comprise of stakeholders, the CMIP Panel co-chairs or Task Team Co-leads of the CMIP Panel and any other WCRP members specified.
46. The interest(s) of the bodies/organisations being sought for the stakeholder panel should be clearly set out.
47. Stakeholder Panel membership should be set out in a table and is on an Ex-Officio basis. It should be reviewed by the appointing body on an annual basis to allow for inclusion of new representatives. It is expected that the position is a representative one, therefore if a member changes institution and/or steps down from project leadership, their appointing body should provide a nomination for replacement.
48. For stakeholder panels with an open appointment process, expressions of interest for a position on the stakeholder panel will be opened at least 6 weeks prior to the annual review of membership and considered during the review process.
49. All stakeholders must report Conflicts of Interest to the co-leads before joining a panel and update their Conflicts of Interest if this change.

50. TABLE: NAME OF STAKEHOLDER PANEL (1 per stakeholder panel)

Member type	Appointment process	Term	Body and position
Co-chair/Co-lead			Appointing body representative
Body Member(s)			Active contribution to body functioning
Stakeholder	Open Call	2y annually reviewed	Provide name of body/consortium/project/organisation and representative name
Stakeholder	Body & PBLM	2y annually reviewed	Provide name of body/consortium/project/organisation and representative name
Stakeholder	Body & PBLM	2y annually reviewed	Provide name of body/consortium/project/organisation and representative name
Stakeholder	Body & PBLM)	2y annually reviewed	Provide name of body/consortium/project/organisation and representative name

Amendments to the ToR

51. Any recommendations for amendments to the Terms of Reference should be submitted to the WGCM for approval and validated by the ESMO SSG. This should include a cover table, using this template, providing a summary of the changes from the approved ToRs:

Page# Section Title, Clause #	Change Description	Rationale/Justification
p8, Meetings & deliverables, Clauses 28-32	Addition of clauses 28-32	To provide more explicit detail regarding CMIP Panel meeting requirements

VERSION RECORD

Version number	Approval body	Date approved
Version 1.0	CMIP Core Panel	18/07/2024

Version1.1	WGCM	13/09/2024
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ANNEX A

CMIP Panel Task Team creation template

This template is copy of the contents of this form <https://bit.ly/propose-new-task-team> which must be completed and submitted to cmip-ipo@esa.int

1. Name of the Task Team
2. Referent Working Group or Project Panel
3. Current members
4. Starting date
5. Planned duration
6. Purpose & objectives
7. Expected outcome
8. Linkage with existing ESMO activities or other WCRP activities if any

ANNEX B

This template is copy of the contents of this form <https://bit.ly/ESMO-Nomination-Form> which must be completed and submitted.

Nomination for [Appointment/Extension]

Nominated for: [Name of the WCRP high-level steering committee]

As: [role of the nominated person, e.g., co-chair, member...]

1. DETAILS OF CANDIDATE NOMINATED

- Title:
- First Name:
- Last Name:
- Year of PhD (or the final academic degree) obtained:
- Nationality (citizenship):
- Residing country:
- Affiliation:
- E-mail Address:

2. MEMBER SINCE & UNTIL (year, in case of extension)

- Expertise vis-à-vis the role of the [WCRP core activity] (maximum of 8 lines):
- Science Background (maximum of 8 lines):
- Positions held (maximum of 8 lines):
- Five most relevant publications
- Why is this individual particularly suited to this [steering committee]? (maximum of 5 lines)

3. SUBMITTED BY

- Title:
- First Name:
- Last Name:
- Organisation: